

Thermally Driven 3D Seamless Textile Actuators for Soft Robotic Applications

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Soft wearable robotic devices have emerged as a promising solution for human mobility assistance and rehabilitation, yet current solutions suffer from issues such as bulkiness, high cost, nonscalability, noise, and limited portability. This study introduces a novel approach to soft robotic assistive devices using untethered, soft actuators with seamlessly integrated sensing, heating, and actuation properties through digital machine knitting and low-boiling liquid. The proposed soft actuator operates under a voltage of less than 12.5 V, generating a tip force of up to 50 mN. This actuator achieves a bending motion when filled with 2 mL of low-boiling liquid and supplied with 15 W. The dynamic response of the actuator is examined under consistent parameters, revealing a 60-second inflation time and a subsequent natural cooling period of 30 s at room temperature. Notably, over 12 cycles, the tip force of the actuator exhibits minimal variation, highlighting its durability for prolonged usage. The proposed approach paves the way for overcoming the limitations of existing technologies, particularly in terms of motion assistance and rehabilitation applications, with an emphasis on at-home usage during daily activities.

1. Introduction

Soft wearable robotic devices have gained attention in the past decade as an attractive solution for human mobility assistance and rehabilitation.^[1,2] Unfortunately, despite the relentless efforts of current research, the present solutions are bulky, highly expensive, nonscalable, noisy, and have limited portability.^[3–7] Therefore, soft robotic assistive devices are incompatible with the range of motion assistance and rehabilitation applications and are restricted to clinical settings. This limits their use for at-home assistance and rehabilitation during activities of daily living.

This article focuses on untethered, soft actuators for potential motion assistance and rehabilitation applications with seamlessly integrated sensing, heating, and actuation properties using digital machine knitting and low-boiling liquid. The proposed

technology is demonstrated through the development of a soft robotic gripper.

One of the most prevalent and rapidly expanding methods of actuation in the soft robotic field for developing assistive devices is the fluid-driven approach.^[8] In this method, fluid such as air is used to pressurize soft actuator pouches with variable stiffness to generate the desired force and motion. Pneumatically powered actuators developed in this manner achieved different motions including rotation, extension, bending, and contraction by anisotropic coding of the actuator structure. The actuator design is dictated by the type of assistance needed for the joint on the human body and the targeted improvement needed for a particular type of motion. Elastomeric material, primarily silicone, has been used for the development of fluidic actuators.^[9–12] Nevertheless, mass production and the labor-intensive fabrication of elastomeric materials necessitated further research to identify superior flexible and light material candidates, such as textiles.

Early in the 2010s, roboticists started to use textiles as a promising class of material for the development and improvement of wearable soft robotic components, including actuators and sensors.^[13] Textiles are an attractive material candidate for wearable soft robotics due to their low weight, breathability, low cost, versatile mechanical properties, and conformability.^[14–17] Textile-based pneumatic actuators use the same actuation mechanism as the elastomer-based actuators, but with less bulk when

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depressurized. All these advantages are key for the development of assistive devices that would efficiently transmit the forces to the end of the kinematic chain without hindering the movement of the user. To develop textile-based fluidic actuators that apply forces and define motions, layers of thin film and fabrics with contrasting mechanical properties are combined making inflatable pouches with anisotropic properties.^[18–20] Textile-based pneumatic actuators have been developed to assist and rehabilitate both upper and lower extremities.^[21–25] A combination of extensible and inextensible fabric layers results in flexion and extension motions when pressurized with air, mimicking the fingers, hand, legs, or wrist motions. For the most part, the techniques used to attach the actuator layers use a cut-and-sew approach and adhesion processes using thermal or welding techniques. The developed actuators are worn on the body part as extra components that are attached to a piece of garment. This particular integration approach deteriorates the reliability of the system. Textile-based soft sensors for motion tracking have also found their way to soft robotics development as an integral component for the actuator operation.^[26–28] Integration of sensors is necessary to establish feedback control methods to ensure that the wearable device applies the wearer’s assistive forces at the right time.^[10] There are drawbacks when using such an open-loop control. For example, it is not clear when the actuator reaches the desired state, or the resulting temporal dynamics may not be optimal without the feedback control.^[29] Given that soft robotics ventures into more comprehensive and demanding applications, sensor information becomes key to achieving high task performance levels. Of particular interest for the purpose of assistive wearable devices are strain and pressure sensors which

are being integrated as attachments on the actuator body.^[26–28,30] Those sensors are developed separately by the integration of conductive textile structural elements (i.e., threads, yarns, and fabrics) into the fabric architecture. The working principle of such sensing fabrics is based on changes in their electrical output upon stretch and/or pressure actions.

State-of-the-art textile-based soft robotics utilizing pneumatic actuators need to have compressors and valves to pressurize actuators to perform their tasks which greatly reduce the mobility of the robotic device.^[18–20,31–35] An alternative approach is the use of thermally powered soft fluidic (TPSF) actuators to eliminate the heavy compressors needed for pumping air to inflate the textile-based pneumatic actuators.^[36–40] TPSF actuators utilize the liquid/vapor phase transition property of low-boiling liquids to generate the desired pressure level for actuation. Soft heating elements are used causing the liquid in the airtight pouch to change its phase to vapor phase that will generate the actuating pressure. This work demonstrates untethered thermally driven knitted soft actuators to overcome current drawbacks related to the wearable soft-robotic system in terms of integration, mobility, and reliability. Therefore, we utilized knitting technology to fabricate various shapes of seamless sensorized actuator shells, as depicted in **Figure 1a**. The actuation mechanism of the system involves the vaporization of a low-boiling liquid (Novec 7100) until the pressure inside the actuator reaches the saturation point. This is achieved using a textile-based heater composed of electrically conductive yarn (Shieldex 235/36 HC + B, resistance: $\leq 600 \Omega \text{ m}^{-1}$), as illustrated in **Figure 1b,c**. Video S1 (Supporting Information) thermal recording provides an in-depth demonstration of the textile-based heater, highlighting

Figure 1. a) The design and fabrication of the actuator. b) Section view of the actuator during actuation by evaporating the low-boiling liquid. c) Thermal image of the textile-based resistive heater on a single actuator and glove during activation. d) Inflated image of the actuator and its layers. e) Operational principle of the knitted conductive yarn loops as resistive sensor and its change in resistance with bending angle. f) Applications of the actuators with the robotic arm and glove.

the precise individual controllability exhibited by each finger of the soft glove that contains Novec 7000. Due to the anisotropic properties of the bottom and top layers of the actuators, the system exhibits the desired motion, as demonstrated in Figure 1d. Additionally, silver-based conductive yarn is knitted to engineer a textile-based resistive sensor on the actuator shells. The operational principle of the sensor involves the separation of conductive knitted loops during actuation, thereby inducing a change in its electrical resistance in Figure 1e.

Furthermore, we employed the manufactured actuator as the end effector (gripper) of an industrial robot and as a soft robotic glove to showcase its capabilities in terms of grasping, carrying, and relocating objects, as illustrated in Figure 1f.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Seamless Knit Actuators

2.1.1. Yarn Selection

In the activation mechanisms, it is crucial to design structures durable against the pressure generated within actuators while facilitating effective movements that rely on the stretchability of the knitted fabric. The yarn selection is also an important parameter for the yarn compatibility with the knitting machine utilized. Rigid and bulkier yarns are influential in producing structures characterized by the desired attributes of firmness and stability. However, due to the fine nature of the Shima Seiki N.SVR 122 Computerized Jacquard Flat Knitting Machine (V-bed) operating at a 14-gauge specification in this study, it is worth noting that such bulkier yarns may demonstrate incompatibility. When handling these yarns with the aim of achieving high loop density or small loop sizes in structures, the needles experience considerable strain and in some instances may even incur breakage. Additionally, introducing multiple loops to a single needle may give rise to potential issues, including entanglement with needles on the opposing bed of the knitting machine, distortion of the tubular structure, or failure of the loops to be securely engaged by the needle.

In the design of knitted fabric-based actuators, achieving distinct movements is possible using different yarns in designated regions. Rigid yarns are utilized in the primary actuator knit, while the strategic incorporation of stretchable yarns in areas where diverse movement properties are desired introduces a nuanced approach. However, this strategic use of stretchable yarns introduces a trade-off, diminishing the overall stability of the actuator and potentially resulting in premature deformations, especially in regions where these yarns undergo repeated movements. Furthermore, the integration of stretchable yarns in actuator designs entails an increased demand for pressure or force to activate movements.

Taking into account various possibilities, the selection of Ne 30/2 cotton yarn, known for its high inelasticity and compatibility with a 14-gauge V-bedded flat knitting machine, has been deemed appropriate. Consequently, this choice enables the activation of simpler designs that demand minimal pressure for actuation.

The choice of yarn involves a 235 f 36 dtex 2-ply HC + B silver-coated polyamide yarn (Shieldex), selected for deployment in the

sensor and heater regions. The rationale behind opting for this highly conductive yarn, characterized by electrical conductivity of $\leq 600 \Omega \text{ m}^{-1}$, lies in its optimal compatibility with the yarn count employed in the ground knit of the designed actuator.

2.1.2. Knitting Selection

In order to predetermine the actuator movements through alterations in the knitting pattern, the applicable knitting patterns for flat knitting machines are the links and ribbed knits. Link knits demonstrate a notable degree of elasticity in the longitudinal (wale) direction, whereas ribbed knits exhibit substantial elasticity in the transverse (course) direction when compared to the former. Another frequently employed knitting pattern in flat knitting machines is the single jersey, where a relatively uniform degree of elasticity in both directions is observed, constrained by loop sizes. Actuator movements can be facilitated by leveraging the inherent flexibility of knitting patterns, achieved through the strategic use of links and ribbed knits in distinct areas. However, it is crucial to note that using these knitting patterns may lead to a reduction in the overall stability of the actuator structure.

Rather than utilizing various knitting patterns for intricate designs that could potentially compromise actuator stability, the choice has been made to opt for the simplest knitting pattern with minimal elasticity—the single jersey. This selection is motivated by the objective of achieving the highest actuator stability while adhering to a straightforward design approach.

2.1.3. Basic Actuator Design

Actuators based on knitted fabric can be configured in a tubular shape, allowing the integration of diverse actuation systems within the fabric. In this study, a rudimentary actuator shell structure was designed utilizing the SDS-ONE APEX4 design system, employing the single jersey knitting pattern.

Contrary to the intricate structures incorporating diverse yarns or patterns, as evidenced in several studies within the literature, a more streamlined approach was adopted. These designs were realized by strategically altering the loop order ratio on the front and back sides of the actuator shell structure in different regions.

The designs were characterized by adherence to monolithic and seamless design principles, omitting the use of other textile production technologies. Open-ended actuator shell structures were purposefully conceived for the exclusive integration of the activation system. Initially, a fundamental actuator design focusing on linear extension was actualized. In this design, the carriage transporting the yarn's carriers traverses toward the right side of the machine, supplying a single type of yarn to the needles on the front bed. It then moves to the left, distributing the same yarn to the needles on the back bed, completing the initial course. Subsequent courses of the design are iteratively executed, mirroring the first course from the closed lower part to the open upper part. A single yarn is fed in a circular manner counterclockwise to all needles within the patterned area on both the front and back beds. Following the foundational design for linear extension, refinements and enhancements were implemented, resulting in the development of C-shaped, hook-shaped, and S-shaped designs in Figure 2a–c.

Figure 2. a–c) Assessment of the required pressure for actuating C-shape, hook-shape, and S-shape actuators. d,e) The effect of production parameters on the turning radius and bending angle of the actuators.

In the enhancement of the O-shaped actuator design, a modification was implemented in the central section of the base design, resulting in six courses of knitting on the back bed corresponding to one course of knitting on the front bed. This adjustment created an accumulation area within the middle segment of the actuator. A repeat pattern was introduced to this accumulation area, allowing for the expansion of the repeat pattern on the flat knitting machine. This modification facilitated a seamless transition from a C-shaped configuration to an O-shaped structure and further evolved into a spiral shape.

The selection of an appropriate loop size for the desired movements necessitated a comprehensive understanding of how different sizes influence the behavior of the actuator. To investigate this, an experiment was conducted wherein a bending actuator design was fabricated with three distinct loop sizes (28, 38, and 48). These sizes were chosen based on the machine configurations, denoting the circumference (measured in inches) of the circular knitting needle capable of producing such loops. Subsequently, the three samples underwent testing under controlled conditions, subject to an applied pneumatic pressure of 123.2 kPa to induce bending. Further details regarding the fabric specifications, such as the loop count per inch in both the course and wale directions, as well as fabric gauge per inch, fabric thickness, and mass density, can be found in Table S1 (Supporting Information). This table provides a comprehensive overview of the key characteristics that define the knit fabric.

The outcome of the experiment, illustrated in Figure 2d, distinctly shows that increments in loop sizes have a direct and linear impact on the widening of the turning radius. It is well-established that with an increase in loop size, the knitted

fabric becomes less dense (lower knitting gauge), resulting in less confined actuator movements.

Another influential factor affecting the degree of actuated bending is the number of accumulated courses on the back side corresponding to a single course on the front side of the actuator. To investigate this factor, an additional experiment was conducted wherein three distinct designs of the bending actuator were crafted with varying amounts of accumulated courses (2, 4, and 6) while maintaining a constant loop size for all courses. In textile science, pintuck refers to the specific ratios within the fabric. The impact of loop size, loop direction, and accumulated courses on mechanical performance has been carefully studied. Figure S1 (Supporting Information) provides a comprehensive overview of the tensile properties of knitted structures, including detailed explanations and analysis. This figure visually demonstrates how variations in loop size, along with course and wale directions and accumulated courses, affect the overall mechanical behavior of the fabric. Increasing pneumatic pressure was applied to each design until their maximum observed bending was achieved. Figure 2e visually represents the requisite pressure for each design and its corresponding bending angle.

The results distinctly reveal that with an increase in the number of accumulated courses, the corresponding bending exhibits a linear increment, coupled with a reduction in the required pressure for the observed bending. These findings suggest a simple relationship: when the accumulation of bending courses is doubled, the required pressure is halved. This relationship is evidenced by the 1:2 ratio achieving a half circle (C shape), the 1:4 ratio completing a full circle (O shape), and the 1:6 ratio reaching one and a half circles (spiral shape).

To realize the hook-shaped actuator design, a modification was applied at the closed end of the base design, resulting in six courses of knitting on the back bed corresponding to one course of knitting on the front bed. This alteration generated an area at the closed end of the actuator, accommodating six accumulations. Subsequently, the design proceeded without further accumulation, maintaining a 1/1 loop order ratio on both the front and back beds. A repeat pattern was incorporated into the accumulation area, providing the flexibility to increase the repeat pattern on the flat knitting machine and thereby adjusting the openness of the hook end.

To realize the S-shaped actuator design, a modification was introduced at the closed end of the base design, involving six courses of knitting on the back bed corresponding to one course of knitting on the front bed. Subsequently, a distinct accumulation area was established, incorporating six courses of knitting on the front bed corresponding to one course on the back bed. Following this enhancement, the knitting design was completed, resulting in the creation of six accumulation areas positioned at both the closed and open ends of the actuator. A repeat pattern was incorporated into these accumulation areas, affording the capability to increase the repeat patterns on the flat knitting machine and, consequently, adjusting the openness of the upper and lower curves of the S shape. In general, machine parameters include loop size, operational speeds (which decrease during intarsia), and the separation of yarn carriers as they exit the knitting area (i.e., the number of needles by which the yarn carriers are kept apart).

2.1.4. Design of Actuator with Sensors and Heaters

Throughout the study, monolithic tube-shaped designs were exclusively realized utilizing a flat knitting machine. Within the design program of the flat knitting machine (Video S2, Supporting Information), tube-shaped structures that are open at one end were created, facilitating the integration of the activation system into actuators.

U-shaped regions demonstrating resistive sensor behavior were knitted on both the front and back surfaces of the O-shaped actuator design, employing conductive yarns, as illustrated in **Figure 3a**. Specifically, the U-shaped conductive area on the non-pintucked surface was designed to fulfill the heating function, while the U-shaped conductive area on the pintucked surface

was designated for data collection during actuator operation, as shown in **Figure 3b–d**.

The application of current to the conductive area on the non-pintucked surface initiates the mechanism responsible for motion activation through actuator heating. Simultaneously, data pertaining to the actuator movement induced by the pressurization of the activation mechanism can be gathered from the conductive area on the pintucked surface. The intarsia technique was employed to seamlessly integrate the areas knitted with conductive yarns, showcasing U-shaped resistive sensor behavior, into the O-shaped actuator design.

The intarsia technique is fundamentally grounded in the principle of knitting multiple loops with different yarns or yarn carriers within a single course. When engaging with multiple yarns or yarn carriers in a single course, preserving the course's integrity necessitates connecting each yarn carrier to the yarns forming the knitting area to its right and left. The SDS-ONE APEX4 design program offers the capability to create basic designs that adhere to the foundational intarsia logic. Notably, this fundamental intarsia logic can be effectively applied in knits executed on a single-knitting machine bed.

In the context of this study, where tube-shaped actuator designs were crafted, the knitting process involved two beds. Each bed incorporated U-shaped areas to be knitted with yarns distinct from those in the ground structure. This entailed the necessity of employing multiple yarn carriers in each course of the loop, rendering the basic intarsia design logic insufficient for tube-shaped actuator designs.

Consequently, for tube-shaped actuator designs integrating sensors and heaters, it became imperative to delineate separately the areas where each carrier knits to create a single course. Additionally, distinct outlines were required for the connections to the areas on the right and left of these knitting areas. The tube-shaped actuator comprises conductive lines on both surfaces to endow heating and sensor capabilities.

2.2. Thermally Driven Actuation Using Low-Boiling Liquid

2.2.1. Operational Principle and Actuation Characteristics

The volume of liquid plays a pivotal role in TPSF actuators, as insufficient quantity hinders complete inflation to the maximum volume. The actuator's performance is intricately linked to the initial liquid volume, as emphasized in previous research.^[41]

Figure 3. a) Side view of the inflated actuator. b) Deflated state of the actuator. c) Illustration of the conductive loop positions on the knit fabric. d) Close-up look at the resistive sensor area.

Injecting excessive amounts results in increased weight and cost of the actuator. Therefore, the bending and volume changes of the actuator are meticulously measured as the liquid volume is calculated, ensuring a constant power supply. The fluid undergoes vaporization until the pressure inside the actuator reaches the saturation point. This is achieved through a textile-based heater constructed from electrically conductive yarn. Conversely, deactivating the heater leads to the cooling and condensation of the fluid, causing the actuator to deflate.

The yarn type, knitting structure, and loop density collectively exert influence on both the movement and dimensions of textile-based actuators during inflation. While various material and design parameters contribute to the actuator's characteristics, our attention is specifically directed toward investigating the impact of loop size and pintuck ratio on the movement of the bending actuator in this study. The bending actuator, inclusive of the thin film and low-boiling liquid, has a weight of 7.65 grams. In its fully deflated state, the actuator measures 12 cm in length and 2 cm in width. The determination of the required liquid volume against pressure values is derived from the general gas equation $PV = nRT$.

$$n_g = \frac{P}{RT} \cdot V_g \quad (1)$$

where n_g is the amount of the substance in moles, P is the absolute pressure of the gas, R is the ideal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature of the gas, and V_g is the volume of the gas. The mass (m) of a material measured in kilograms (kg) can be determined using the formula

$$m = Mn_g \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (2)$$

In this formula, M represents the molar mass of the substance, measured in grams per mole (g mol^{-1}). For instance, the molar mass of 3M Novec 7100 Engineered Fluid is 250 g mol^{-1} . Additionally, the density of Novec 7100, represented by ρ , is 1520 kg m^{-3} .

To determine the necessary volume of liquid (V_l) based on the desired pressure value, the maximum volume of the actuator filled with gas (V_g) is calculated for a rectangular thin-film pouch, which was used in the bending actuators, using Equation (3)–(5).

$$V_l = \frac{m}{\rho} \quad (3)$$

$$V_l = \frac{Mn_g \cdot 10^{-3}}{\rho} \quad (4)$$

$$V_l = \frac{M}{\rho} \cdot \frac{P}{RT} \cdot V_g \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (5)$$

It is noteworthy to mention that according to the equation derived from the general gas equation,^[42] the calculated liquid amount required to fully evaporate and fill the actuator with gas is 0.146 mL. However, this quantity proves adequate only for chamber filling and falls short of providing the desired bending and tip force. Accounting for liquid leakage through the thin-film pores and the textile heater's capabilities, additional liquid injection into the actuator becomes necessary. Furthermore, as

the volume of injected liquid increases, the heightened volume demands more heat for vaporization, given its higher heat capacity. This, in turn, delays the initiation of inflation. Over time, the rise in pressure-induced boiling point becomes apparent, leading to an excess of vapor within the pouch. Consequently, a significant condensation rate ensues, continuously increasing until it aligns with the boiling rate. This alignment triggers a subsequent drop in pressure.^[43]

The actuator, filled with 2 mL of liquid, was subjected to actuation at 12.5 V. **Figure 4a** illustrates the recorded surface temperature of the textile heater using a thermal imaging camera. The experimental conditions were maintained at room temperature ($22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to ensure temperature uniformity, and the power supply was discontinued upon reaching $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to prevent heater deterioration. The characterization tests were repeated five times to confirm the reliability and consistency of the results, and the experimental setup is visually presented in **Figure S2** and **Video S3** (Supporting Information). Voltage-dependent temperature graph is presented in **Figure 4b** depicting the temperature change of the textile heater over a given time duration under constant voltages. This figure illustrates the immediate response to temperature increase within the specified timeframe. **Figure 4c** shows the temperature change over an extended time duration, providing a more comprehensive view of how temperature evolves over a longer period and offering insights into the system's behavior and stability under sustained voltage conditions. To assess actuation time and the power supply necessary for heating the low-boiling liquid, trials were conducted at varying voltages (5, 7.5, 10, and 12.5 V). The results revealed that 5 and 7.5 V were insufficient to activate the heater up to the boiling point of the liquid within the required timeframe. However, between 10 and 12.5 V, the latter proved capable of achieving the required temperature much faster, significantly influencing the response time performance of the actuators.

The power difference test was conducted to determine the optimal power input for managing the actuators. The actuator, filled with 2 mL of liquid, underwent intermittent power supply to facilitate controlled temperature maintenance and prevent overheating over time. Upon reaching the target temperature of $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the external sensor interrupted the power supply until the temperature slightly exceeded the phase-change level of the utilized liquid ($75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Subsequently, the heater was repowered, as illustrated in **Figure 4d**.

Figure 4e illustrates the bending angle changes and controllability of the actuators under 7.5, 12.5, and 15 V. The results indicate that 7.5 V was insufficient to fully inflate the actuator due to inadequate energy for evaporation. Nevertheless, a slight rise in bending angle was observed when the low thermal energy generated by the application of 7.5 V was present. In the case of 12.5 V, a notable bending angle of 140° was achieved, accompanied by a swift phase change of the liquid within 150 s. Consequently, the rest of the experiments were conducted using this optimized power supply. Notably, our observations revealed that subjecting the textile heater to 15 V resulted in a malfunction of the heater, as depicted in **Figure 4d,e**, followed by liquid leakage caused by the melting of the thin film. It is therefore advised to refrain from exceeding the 12.5 V threshold for our textile-based heater integrated actuator.

Figure 4. a) Thermal camera images of a 1:2 pin-tuck ratio bending actuator. b,c) Temperature increase of the textile-based heater under varying voltages. d) Instantaneous power supply and e) bending angle change over time under different voltages. f) The current drawn by the actuator, providing also the break intervals. g) Bending angle and energy consumption change under 12.5 V of voltage. h) Measurement of relative resistance over the bending angle. i,j) The cyclic test results of relative resistance and tip force.

To reduce actuation time and lower the heating temperature, experiments were conducted using 3 M Novec 7000 Engineered Fluid, which has a boiling point of 34 °C. By maintaining the textile-based heater temperature between 55 and 60 °C, the actuation time could be reduced to 120 s, making it more suitable and

safer for wearable applications, as illustrated in Figure S3 (Supporting Information).

The analysis of the conducted tests revealed that 7.5 V proved insufficient to attain the target temperature, resulting in an absence of observed breaks in power supply intervals. In contrast,

supplying 12.5 V facilitated intermittent power application, effectively sustaining the temperature within the required range. The current drawn by the textile heater at 12.5 V intervals is depicted in Figure 4f. In the initial 40 s, the current gradually increases up to 1.5 A while the bending of the actuator initiates. Following the break intervals, the actuator consistently draws a current level similar to that observed before the breaks, indicating the persistence of the actuator's bending.

As the actuator advances toward a bending angle of 140°, the recorded energy consumption exhibits a consistent and parallel increase over time, as illustrated in Figure 4g. This noteworthy pattern not only showcases the actuator's performance but also supports the identification of the optimum voltage value. Additionally, this graph further confirms the uniformity of the seamless actuators, highlighting their stability and reliability.

In the bending characterization, as depicted in Figure 4h, the bending actuator is powered with 12.5 V and maintained within the temperature range of 75–85 °C. Notably, the actuator, featuring a 1:2 pintuck ratio and a loop size of 36, exhibits a 0.25

relative increase in resistance up to a 50° bending angle. This increase is attributed to the changing length of the loop segments of the conductive yarn during force loading. After the 50° bending point, the resistance gradually decreases. This phenomenon can be attributed to the heat received by the resistive sensor and the increased real contact between touching points of adjacent loops and sinker loops.

In the tip force cycle test, the textile heater was powered with 12.5 V and maintained at a constant temperature between 85 and 95 °C for 1 min in each cycle to acquire the necessary thermal energy. Subsequently, a cooling period at room temperature (22 °C) for 30 s followed, leading to liquid condensation and a subsequent drop in force to 0 as the temperature fell below 61 °C, the phase-change point. This setup allowed us to measure the tip force over time, as illustrated in Figure S4 (Supporting Information). Additionally, the change in resistance and tip force during one cycle of heating for 60 s and cooling for 30 s is depicted in Figure S5 (Supporting Information). This procedure was iterated 12 times, and the obtained values reveal that the

Figure 5. a) The mechanical property of the actuator constitutive material. b) The boundary condition of the simulation. c) The mesh view of the model. d) Comparison of the simulation images with real images. e) Verification of the simulation result with experiment.

actuator's tip force exhibited no significant change over the course of this cycle. Although a slight decrease in sensor resistance was observed during the initial cycles as in Figure 4i,j, the cyclic test assures the sturdiness of the manufactured actuators, indicating their suitability for real-life applications.

2.3. Simulation Procedure

The numerical study was conducted using the commercially available Abaqus2021 software. The bending actuator was

designed employing two sheets with a separation distance of 0.1 mm. Each side was defined as a shell/extrusion plane and connected using a tie constraint. The top edge of both planes was fully fixed, and equal pressure was applied to each plane in opposite directions. The nonlinear constitutive model (Marlow) was used to import the mechanical properties of the materials into the simulation software.

Figure 5 illustrates the mechanical properties of each side of the presented bending actuator (a), boundary conditions (b), mesh view (c), the comparison of the simulation images with real

Figure 6. a) Outer and inner control diagrams for the sample system. b) Actuator samples in various shapes. c) Actuator capability of handling different objects varying in shapes and weights. d) Soft robotic glove and its thermal image during actuation. e) Glove capability of handling different objects.

images (d), and the verification of the numerical and experimental deformation (e). Two thousand linear quadrilateral elements of type S4R were implemented. The error between the experimental and simulation results is $\approx 5.09\%$.

2.4. System Identification

System identification holds paramount importance in sensor and actuator design as it consolidates crucial information regarding system stability, controllability, performance, efficiency, operating range determination, cost functions, robustness, and reliability.^[44] Leveraging the MATLAB System Identification Toolbox models in both the time and frequency domains was established to characterize the resistance-angle relationship for the sensor and the angle-power relationship for the actuator. Access to these models empowers individuals to gain insights into crucial aspects such as the stability and controllability of actuators and sensors. Furthermore, it facilitates experimentation in a simulation environment, enabling a deeper understanding of these aspects.

$$\frac{R(s)}{\Theta(s)} = \frac{0.20}{5.77 \cdot 10^4 s^4 + 1.12 \cdot 10^4 s^3 + 1.03 \cdot 10^3 s^2 + 51.04s + 1} \quad (6)$$

$$5.77 \cdot 10^4 \frac{d^4 r(t)}{dt^4} + 1.12 \cdot 10^4 \frac{d^3 r(t)}{dt^3} + 1.03 \cdot 10^4 \frac{d^2 r(t)}{dt^2} + 51.04 \frac{dr(t)}{dt} + r(t) = 0.20\theta(t)u(t) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\Theta(s)}{P(s)} = \frac{e^{-0.34s} \cdot 1.13 \cdot 10^4}{2.56 \cdot 10^7 s^3 + 2.11 \cdot 10^6 s^2 + 1.90 \cdot 10^5 s + 1} \quad (8)$$

$$2.56 \cdot 10^7 \frac{d^3 \theta(t)}{dt^3} + 2.11 \cdot 10^6 \frac{d^2 \theta(t)}{dt^2} + 1.90 \cdot 10^5 \frac{d\theta(t)}{dt} + \theta(t) = 1.13 \cdot 10^4 p(t - 0.34)u(t - 0.34) \quad (9)$$

where θ , p , r , u , and t denote angle, power, resistance, unit step function, and time, respectively, where $u(t - 0.34)$ accounts for a dead time of 0.34 s. Capital letters represent them in the Laplace domain. Examining the characteristic equations, specifically the denominator coefficients, reveals that although both systems exhibit significant delay times, the resistive sensor manifests considerably less delay, rendering it highly suitable for the system. Equation (6) represents the s-domain or frequency domain transfer function, while Equation (7) outlines the time domain differential equation of the sensor. Similarly, Equation (8) captures the transfer function, and Equation (9) portrays the time domain differential equation of the actuator. Both transfer functions illustrate stable dynamics, with the actuator exhibiting controllability despite a small dead time. The coefficients are all positive in all equations, which shows the input-output relations are stable.

2.5. Application Demonstration

The manufactured actuator has been integrated as the gripper end of an industrial robot, as depicted in **Figure 6a**. The control diagram outlines the robotic system, comprising a thermally driven 3D seamless textile actuator functioning as a gripper, in conjunction with an industrial robotic arm. Furthermore, the seamless knitting technique proves to be versatile, allowing

for the production of actuators in various shapes, with or without a heater/sensor. This capability is showcased in **Figure 6b**, which displays seamless knitted actuators taking the form of S, O, F, and T, inflated using a knitted heating mat as a demonstrative illustration.

Our textile-based soft gripper and glove have demonstrated their efficacy in grasping, carrying, and relocating objects with varying shapes and weights, as illustrated in **Figure 6c–e**. Specifically, an O-shaped actuator was chosen for effective gripping, as it can completely enclose the object being lifted. Matching the inner diameter of the actuator with the circumference of the object ensures full contact and secure handling. While larger and heavier objects may cause the actuator to expand, it maintains reasonable control by naturally bringing its two ends closer together. The actuator successfully accommodated a marker pen due to the matching inner diameter and lightweight nature. In the case of a 60 mL syringe, although lightweight, its larger circumference required the actuator to expand, as demonstrated in **Video S4** (Supporting Information). Conversely, the actuator effortlessly lifted a coffee mug, and the soft robotic glove could hold a syringe and a plastic bottle, showcasing its capability to handle significantly greater weight when power was supplied to the resistive heater.

3. Conclusion

In this study, we propose a novel approach for textile-based soft actuators with seamlessly integrated sensing, heating, and actuation properties through the digital knitting machine and gas-liquid phase transition of the low-boiling liquid for soft robotic assistive and rehabilitation devices. The actuation mechanism is triggered by a textile-based heat transmission system, aiming to eliminate the challenges associated with pneumatic and hydraulic actuation systems, such as bulkiness and heaviness, as well as drive noise. This approach enhances portability and reduces noise, offering significant advantages for soft robotic assistive and rehabilitation devices while lowering manufacturing costs.

Actuation of the produced textile actuators is facilitated by the pressure generated from vaporized liquid, enabling them to exhibit high forces and large expansions due to their inherent stretchable and flexible nature. The proposed soft actuator operates under a voltage of less than 12.5 V, proficiently generating a tip force of up to 50 mN. Introducing 2 mL of low-boiling liquid and applying 15 W result in the successful generation of bending motion. While keeping the above parameters and environmental test conditions constant, we also investigated the dynamic response of the actuator, revealing a 60-second full inflation time and a subsequent 30-second natural cooling period at room temperature. Furthermore, the actuator's tip force did not show a notable change during cycling testing, demonstrating its durability for prolonged usage.

As the field of soft robotics experiences rapid growth, progress in manufacturing techniques and potential applications of these soft actuators holds great importance. Hence, eliminating the aforementioned limitations in actuation is crucial to moving forward. We believe that the proposed system has great potential in manipulative tasks, such as developing soft robotic grippers for

automated crop harvesting or emulation of human finger movements to create a soft exoskeleton glove.

4. Experimental Section

Heating Mat Design: The activation of the designed actuator structures in this study relies on heat, and to achieve this, a heater mat design was meticulously crafted. The intention was to generate the required heat for the actuators to demonstrate their movements when placed on a flat surface. Several knitting techniques, including plain knit, rib knit, and interlock knit, were experimentally explored to ensure the stability and prevention of curling when the heating mat is positioned on a flat surface. The conducted experiments conclusively demonstrated that the desired shape was achieved with the heating mat produced using a 1×1 rib knit.

The heating mat design features resistor structures that are heated by electrical current. The creation of these resistor structures involved the use of conductive yarns and the fundamental intarsia technique outlined in Section 2.1.4. Ground yarn for the heating mats was Ne 24/2 cotton yarn (Karan Tekstil Inc.), while the integration of resistor areas employed 235 f 36 dtex 2-ply HC + B silver-coated polyamide yarn (Shieldex). A series of experiments were conducted to determine the dimensions of the resistor areas that ensure compatibility with the power supply used for heating while achieving the required resistance values. The results of these experiments, showcasing the resistor area dimensions and the appearance of the heating mat, can be observed in Figure 6b.

Thermally Driven 3D Seamless Textile Actuator Characterization: The characterization tests for thermally driven 3D seamless textile actuators encompassed the comparison of actuators with varying shapes. The evaluation includes an analysis of pressure-bending angle changes based on the course ratio, heating characteristics, actuator bending behavior, sensor performance, and cycle tests. Detailed explanations of all measurement systems employed in the characterization tests are provided in Section "Components of Experiments", categorized as components. Additionally, Section "Experimental Setup" elaborates on the components utilized during the tests.

Components of Experiments: The experimental setup designed for the tests incorporate various components, including the air pressure system, angle detection system, temperature control system, thermal camera, digital multimeter, power supply, universal tensile machine with force gauge, and an industrial robotic arm. Specifically, the air pressure system, angle detection system, and temperature control systems featured custom-designed software and hardware, whereas the remaining components were commercially available products.

The air pressure system comprised specific components, including an air pump (DC 12 V/370-02PM-SKU-5000, Makeblock, Shenzhen, China), two solenoid valves (12 V 2W-025-08, Senya), a pressure sensor (MPXHZ-6250 A-C6T1, Freescale Semiconductor, USA), a microcontroller (Arduino Nano, ATmega328P), a button, a power supply (Mervesan, MT-100-12, 12 V 8.5 A, Turkey), an engine driver (L298N Driver Board), and a metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistor driver (IRLZ44). The microcontroller assumed control of the entire system. When the inflate button was pressed, the air pump activated via the motor driver, pressurizing the air. Subsequently, the inflate valve opened, facilitating air flow into the actuator. Upon releasing the button, both the air pump and inflate valve closed. Pressing the deflate button opened the deflate valve, releasing the air from the actuator into the atmosphere. The microcontroller transmitted air pressure information within the actuator to the computer at a sampling frequency of 50 Hz.

The angle detection system comprised a webcam (Logitech C922 Pro, China) and custom-developed software. Image processing methods were employed to detect labels positioned on the endpoints and peak points of the actuator. The system operated at a sampling frequency of 10 Hz. The calculation of the angle at the peak point was carried out using the cosine formula, as outlined below.

$$\alpha = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{b^2 + c^2 - a^2}{2 \cdot b \cdot c} \right) \quad (10)$$

where α represents the angle formed by the labels at the endpoints with the label at the peak, b is the distance between the first endpoint and the peak point, c is the distance between the second endpoint and the peak point, and a is the distance between the endpoints.^[45] The bending angle, β , indicative of the flexion angle of the actuator, was calculated using the value of α as follows.

$$\beta = 360 - 2 \cdot \alpha \quad (11)$$

The temperature control system consisted of an infrared temperature sensor (MLX90614-DCI, DFRobot, Shanghai, China), a relay board (4 Channel 5 V), a current sensor (ACS712, Allegro MicroSystems, Massachusetts, USA), an on-off switch, and a microcontroller (Arduino Mega, Atmega 2560). The primary purpose of the temperature control system is to prevent overheating of the conductive yarns used as heaters. It maintains the temperature within preassigned lower and upper threshold values based on temperature information obtained from the sensor. When the temperature exceeds the upper threshold value, it interrupts the electrical current from the power source through the relay. Conversely, when the temperature falls below the lower threshold value, it restores the electrical current to the conductive yarns via the relay. Instantaneous power and energy information were acquired through the connected current sensor in the system. The on-off switch initiated the cycle test. For the cycle test, the microcontroller was preprogrammed with information about the active and passive durations of energy. As long as the energy was active, the temperature was maintained within predetermined threshold values. After the specified duration, the energy was cut off, and the actuator was allowed to cool for the passive duration. The microcontroller orchestrated all these processes. Additionally, information such as temperature, current, relay position, cycle count, and status was transmitted to the computer at a sampling frequency of 50 Hz. The other commercially sourced components and their intended purposes are listed below.

Thermal Camera (885-1 9 Hz, Testo, Germany): It is used for real-time observation of heat distribution and validation of temperature information in the thermal control system.

Digital Multimeter (34465 A, Keysight, California, USA): It is utilized for collecting resistance information from the resistive sensor at a sampling frequency of 20 Hz.

Power Supply (2231 A-30-3, Keithley Instruments, Ohio, USA): It is used to transfer electrical energy to the heater created with the conductive yarn. Experiments were conducted under constant voltages by adjusting the maximum current.

Force Gauge (M5-50, Mark-10, New York, USA): It is employed to obtain force information for cycle tests. Data was collected at a sampling frequency of 50 Hz.

Universal Tensile Machine (ESM303, Mark-10, New York, USA): It is used for positioning the actuator and force gauge during cycle tests.

Industrial Robotic Arm (GP8, Yaskawa, Slovenia): It is responsible for holding the actuator during cycle tests and applications. It was also used to bring the object to the appropriate position by holding the object of the actuator in applications.

In this study, distinct data acquisition programs were created for the air pressure system, temperature control system, digital multimeter, and force gauge employed in measurements. Device data were recorded on the computer at their designated sampling frequencies. For the angle detection system, real-time recording of angle values and images captured from the camera was implemented. Experiment-specific components were integrated into the system, and data were gathered using the respective data acquisition programs. To consolidate the collected data, an interpolation method based on the recording time was employed.

Experimental Setup: In this section, the components used in the experiments for the characterization of thermally driven 3D seamless textile actuators are explained, along with the specific configurations employed in the experiments.

In Figure 2, the comparisons of actuators with different shapes and the tests for pressure and bending angle changes based on the course ratio were conducted using pressurized air. For these tests, the air pressure system and the bending angle system were used in conjunction. The bending angle information was obtained in relation to the applied pressure.

In Figure 4a–h, the characterization tests of thermally driven 3D actuators were conducted using the angle detection system, temperature control system, thermal camera, digital multimeter, and power supply. The actuator was operated with predetermined voltages. The bending angle, heater temperature, instantaneous current supplied to the heater, sensor resistance, and system status information were collected in real-time using developed programs for the respective components. After collecting the data, it was processed, combined, and visualized. Real-time validation of temperature information was performed using the thermal camera, and video recording was conducted. In Figure 4i,j, the results of the shared cycle test were presented. The used components were the temperature control system, thermal camera, digital multimeter, power supply, universal tensile test machine, force gauge, and robotic arm. The robotic arm was responsible for holding the actuator. The force gauge connected to the universal tensile machine measured the applied tip force. The universal tensile machine was also utilized to adjust the force gauge to the appropriate height. The cycle test in the temperature control system was initiated with the on/off button. Heating was provided for a specified duration using the heater, followed by allowing the actuator to cool. Tip force from the force gauge, sensor resistance from the digital multimeter, and current and temperature information from the thermal control system were obtained. This process was repeated for 16 cycles, considering the first 4 cycles as the warm-up cycle. The results of the subsequent 12 tests were then shared.

In Figure 6c, the application demonstration showcases the use of the thermal control system and robotic arm. The thermally driven 3D seamless textile actuator grips the object by bending. The robotic arm then carries the object held by the actuator to a box. Subsequently, the actuator, having stored energy, releases the object, delivering it to the box. Thus, the system completes the assigned task.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

O.A. took care of conceptualization, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, supervision, validation, writing the original draft preparation, and writing the review and editing. K.O. took care of conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, resources, software, validation, visualization, writing the original draft,

and writing the review and editing. C.G. took care of conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, resources, validation, visualization, writing the original draft preparation, and writing the review & editing. I.A.K.A. took care of conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualization, and writing the original draft. A.F. took care of conceptualization, investigation, methodology, and visualization. M.F.C. took care of data curation, formal analysis, investigation, resources, validation, visualization, and writing the review & editing. M.S.C. took care of conceptualization, investigation, methodology, resources, writing the original draft, validation, supervision, visualization, and writing the review and editing. B.T. took care of formal analysis, visualization, and writing the original draft. A.T.A. took care of conceptualization, methodology, project administration, supervision, validation, and writing the review and editing. G.I. took care of project administration, supervision, validation, and writing the review & editing.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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3D knitting, low-boiling liquids, resistive sensors, soft robotics, textile heaters, thermoactive actuators, wearable robotics

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